

Weight Stigma and Self-Esteem in the Saudi Community: Statistics on Obesity and Its Associated Illnesses

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ABSTRACT

Background: Weight stigma refers to negative attitudes and beliefs that undervalue people based on their weight status. In our study, we aimed to assess weight-associated stigma and self-esteem among people in Saudi Arabia.

Methods: We utilized a descriptive, cross-sectional, correlational research design and asked a convenience sample of 308 persons from the Saudi community to fill out an electronically designed questionnaire. Along with the Weight Self-Stigma Questionnaire (WSSQ) and the Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSE), the questionnaire encompassed some sociodemographic data, biometric measures like weight and height, and medical history. Piloting, validity, and reliability testing of the questionnaire were done, and we used the tools without amendment.

Results: More than two-fifths of the study sample were obese, whereas about one-third of them were overweight. The study revealed a significant negative correlation between the BMI of the participants and both their mean WSSQ and RSE scales. However, we detected a positive significant correlation between the mean RSE scale and the mean WSSQ.

Conclusion: The mean WSSQ was a significant independent predictor of the participants' mean RSE scale. Female, older, and smoking participants had significantly higher weight stigma feelings compared to others, while married participants had lower self-esteem feelings compared to single participants. Having a higher BMI was significantly correlated with some chronic illnesses such as osteoarthritis, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, obesity, and osteoporosis. A psychoeducational program is one of the key recommended interventions to increase public awareness about weight management and weight stigma in communities.

Keywords: Chronic illnesses, obesity, Saudi Arabia, self-esteem, weight stigma.

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Introduction

According to Kopelman (2007) and Althumiri, Basyouni, AlMousa, et al. (2021), obesity is a major risk factor for a variety of physical and mental health issues, including

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cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, heart attacks, strokes, and depression. According to Pereira-Miranda et al. (2017) and Neumark-Sztainer et al. (2002), obesity has a negative impact on well-being by causing binge eating,

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increased body dissatisfaction, depression, and the employment of improper weight control techniques. Obesity continues to be one of the most urgent health concerns of our time because of its significant effects on physical and mental health and well-being (Althumiri, Basyouni, & BinDhim, 2021).

Weight stigma refers to negative attitudes and beliefs that undervalue people based on their weight status, which may include prejudice, discrimination, stereotyping, and social segregation, and, although experienced by people of all weights, is mainly focused on people living with obesity (Brewis et al., 2018). Also, Wu and Berry (2018) demarcated the experience of verbal or physical abuse secondary to being overweight or obese. Experiences with weight stigma can have serious negative effects, such as lowered self-esteem, reduced psychosocial health, depressed mood, and increased metabolic risk factors (Eisenberg et al., 2006; Hunger & Major, 2015).

Both children and adults who experience weight discrimination are more likely to transition from being overweight to being obese compared with those who do not experience weight discrimination (Jackson et al., 2014; Quick et al., 2013) and this likelihood may contribute to health disparities and increased risk of mortality. Research has also shown that experiencing weight stigma is associated with increased stress and calorie consumption, which can lead to weight gain (Hunger & Tomiyama, 2014; Jackson et al., 2014; Sutin et al., 2015). Stigmatization signals may come from coworkers and employers (Watson et al., 2018), academics (Cameron, 2016), health care workers (Tomiyama et al., 2018), or partners and family members (Hunger et al., 2015). Weight-related stigmatization has a detrimental effect on a person's physical health (O'Brien et al., 2016; Wu & Berry, 2018), psychological well-being such as lower self-esteem, anxiety, depression, and eating disorders (Kahan & Puhl, 2017; Walsh et al., 2018), and daily functioning such as using unhealthy coping mechanisms, binge-eating, or avoiding exercise (Wu & Berry, 2018).

Goffman (1988) found that stigma originates from civilizations' tendency to define categories based on characteristics that are seen as common or typical in humans, forming a sense of social identity. As a result, those who differ from these features are thought to carry a stigma. In light of this, a person who is stigmatized is one whose social identity includes any characteristic that defies the norms of the society in question. The society stops viewing them as an ordinary being and instead starts to characterize them as weak, defective, disadvantageous, or discreditable.

The stigma attached to being overweight is the denigration of a person for being heavier than the ideal in a certain society (Goffman, 1988). One of the first things people notice about someone is their weight, which is an obvious physical trait that cannot be concealed (Puhl & Heuer, 2009). In this context, it is clear that the person who is overweight carries a significant social stigma because they are deemed ineligible for full social acceptability, suffer exclusion in a variety of contexts, and may even see their social identity and personal trust deteriorate (Goffman, 1988). The most prevalent kind of stigma is personal (microsocial), which refers to the unique psychological process that a person goes through in instances where they encounter prejudice and discrimination. However, according to Corrigan et al. (2005), corporate and governmental institutional actions, such as different types of prejudice and discrimination, limit the opportunity for stigmatized (macrosocial) groups to overcome so-called structural stigma. Both types also have negative effects. Self-stigma is the internalization of stigma brought on by personal stigma encountered through individual attacks, resulting in beliefs and actions based on the notion that a large body is twisted and immoral. However, structural stigma can also manifest itself overtly, as it does in bullying situations, or it may even be covered up by a health discourse.

Rosenberg (1965) defined self-esteem as having a positive perspective on oneself. Mental, physical, and social components all

contribute to self-esteem. Değirmenci et al. (2015) have shown that obese people have lower self-esteem, whereas some scientists did not find a correlation between obesity and self-esteem (Ozmen et al., 2007; Renman et al., 1999).

Scholars have reported that youths with obesity are allegedly more likely than those without obesity to have depression, behavioral issues, poor body image (BI), and low self-esteem, in addition to a higher risk of developing noncommunicable diseases (Erermis et al., 2004; Muris et al., 2005). Self-esteem and BI satisfaction were found to be significantly correlated in one research study on adults that included college students (Koyuncu et al., 2010). Moreover, constant stigma compromises mental and physical well-being, leads to weight gain, and feeds the stigma's root cause (Puhl & Brownell, 2006). People who are overweight may absorb the stigma after being subjected to it repeatedly in a variety of social settings (Kahan & Puhl, 2017; Pearl & Puhl, 2016; Pearl et al., 2015), which can lead to an inferior self-image.

The significance of reducing weight stigma is obvious given that the prevalence of obesity in Saudi Arabia is rising and is predicted to reach 41% of men and 78% of women by 2022 (Al-Quwaidhi et al., 2014). Previous studies documented that in several Arab nations, exposure to mass media has been linked to a shift in the perception of the ideal body type (Al Saud et al., 2019; Musaiger & Al-Mannai, 2014). According to a 2014 survey, most Saudi women think that being overweight leads to social stigma and morally dubious behavior (Alqout & Reynolds, 2014).

The aim and objectives of the study

Aim: In our study, we aimed to assess weight-associated stigma and self-esteem among people in Saudi Arabia.

Objectives: The current study has the following objectives:

- to assess the weight stigma among the general population in Saudi Arabia
- to assess the self-esteem among the population of Saudi Arabia
- to determine common physical chronic illnesses among the participants

- to identify the association between weight stigma and self-esteem among the population of Saudi Arabia

- to explore the correlation between the participants' weight or body mass index and physical illnesses or chronic diseases

Materials and methods

Research design and setting

We undertook the descriptive, cross-sectional, correlational research design study in the kingdom of Saudi Arabia because of the convenience, accessibility of research subjects, and availability of researchers in this nation.

Study sample

We recruited a convenience sample of 308 participants from the adult population of Saudi Arabia. We calculated the sample size according to the target population of Saudi Arabia and estimated the sample based on the total size of the adult populace by using OpenEpi free software version 3.1 (Dean et al., 2013). The minimal sample size required was 271 persons to achieve a 90% confidence interval with 5% confidence limits, 50% anticipated frequency, and a design effect value of 1.0. We increased the sample of participants recruited in this study to 308 to ensure the achievement of the targeted confidence level.

Tools for data collection

We carried out the data collection using an electronic survey that encompassed the following personal characteristics of the study participants: age, gender, marital status, level of education, occupation, smoking status, and diagnoses with chronic illnesses.

According to the categories used by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), we calculated each participant's Body Mass Index (BMI) using self-reported weight, height, and height in meters squared (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2022). We sorted participants into the following categories based on their BMIs: Underweight (<18.5 kg/m²), appropriate or healthy weight (18.5–24.9 kg/m²), overweight (25.0–29.9 kg/m²), and obese (≥30.0 kg/m²). The categories were all

determined using standard internationally accepted BMI cutoffs.

Tool (I) The Weight Self-Stigma Questionnaire (WSSQ)

The WSSQ is a 12-item Likert scale that assesses weight-related self-stigmatization. It comprises two subscales that each assess (1) self-devaluation caused by weight, and (2) fear of enacted stigma. The questionnaire's initial version had sound psychometrics and a reliable preliminary construct. The entire scale's ($=0.878$) and the two subscales' ($=0.869$ and $=0.812$) Cronbach coefficients were acceptable, and principal component analyses identified a two-factor structure (Lillis et al., 2010). Ratings for WSSQ items ranged from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). We computed both the total scale and each subscale's sum scores. The self-devaluation subscale (factor 1) comprises items 1–6, and the dread-of-enacted-stigma subscale (factor 2) comprises items 7–12; However, there are no items with reversed scores in the WSSQ scale.

Tool (II) The Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (RSE)

These researchers adopted and translated the RSE (Rosenberg, 1979). It consists of 10 statements (5 statements are phrased positively and 5 statements are phrased negatively). The positive statements (#1, 3, 4, 7, 10) were rated on a scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Scoring for the negative statements (# 2, 5, 6, 8, 9) was reversed, i.e., 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree). According to these answers, cumulative scoring for each individual ranged from 10 to 50, with 50 indicating the highest possible score. For the scoring system of the RSE scale, the higher the RSE score, the greater the self-esteem, and vice versa.

Pilot study

Before the main investigation, we conducted a pilot study on 10% of the required study sample to assess the clarity of the scales, the viability of the study, and the applicability of the data collection technology. According to the findings of the pilot study, an average respondent needed 15–20 minutes to complete the entire questionnaire, depending on their understanding and cooperation.

Based on the findings of the pilot study, we refined the questionnaire, and excluded the pilot study participants from the main study population. We further evaluated the validity of the employed scales using the results of the pilot study.

Validity and reliability

A panel of five experts in the fields of psychiatric mental health nursing and medical-surgical nursing reviewed the tool to test the content and face validity of the questionnaire and deemed it acceptable. We determined reliability using Cronbach's alpha coefficient test, which revealed that both scales (WSSQ and RSE) consisted of relatively homogenous items, as indicated by the moderate to high reliability (internal consistency) of each scale (Cronbach's alpha coefficients were 0.825 and 0.793 respectively).

Procedure

We electronically solicited potential responders for the pilot and main studies through the researchers' social networks, friends, and coworkers. We created the online survey using Google Forms and sent it to participants through various social media channels (WhatsApp, Messenger, Facebook, and Imo). Our data handling practices complied with all applicable national data protection regulations. Participants were given a debriefing of the questionnaire, the study did not include any type of deceit, and only anonymous data were gathered. The data collection procedure was carried out over March and April of 2022.

Ethical considerations

Participants in this study gave their full consent to participate without any kind of coercion or compensation. Before responding to the questionnaire, participants were required to read and approve the included informed consent. The study proposal was approved by the Institutional Review Board of Mohammad Al-Mana College for Medical Science in Saudi Arabia before we embarked on data collection (Ethical Approval # SR/IRB/37-1/22). Before they participated in the study, we made the subjects aware of the study's goals and design, as well as the

researchers' affiliations and contact information. We also made them aware of their right to decline participation or to withdraw from the study at any time. Because no identifying information—such as names, email addresses, or mobile numbers—was collected from the participants and their responses were fully anonymous, the inclusion of questionnaire identification numbers helped to limit any potential confidentiality breaches. The only foreseeable consequences of completing the questionnaire were discomfort or annoyance. We fully adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki's ethical guidelines for medical research involving human participants to conduct this research (World Medical Association, 2018).

Statistical analysis

We used the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 23, for statistical analysis of the study findings (IBM Corp, 2015). Descriptive statistics, such as the mean and standard deviation or number and percentage, were used to present the data. For categorical variables, the number and percentage were utilized, whereas the mean and standard deviation were used for continuous variables. Because each question had to be answered before going on to the next, no missing data were discovered.

We used the correlation coefficient test to identify the presence and significance of the relationship between variables of interest, and the correlation was significant at $P < 0.05$. Linear and multiple regression tests were used to identify and predict the significant independent predictors of the main variables of the study. Some data are also shown using figures and graphs to illustrate them in simple and meaningful representations.

Results

The results of our current study are illustrated in the following tables and graphs. The subjects in the current study were 308 persons from different sociodemographic backgrounds in the Saudi community. **Table 1** shows that more than 70% of the participants were females compared to only 29.9% who were males. Almost one-third of the participants were aged 19–29 years, followed by participants aged 40–49 years (27.3%), 30–39 years (24.7%), and 50–59 years (15.6%).

More than half of the participants were married (64.9%), and 54.5% were educated to the level of a bachelor's degree. Most had a job and were working (61%), whereas others were students (24.7%), unemployed (7.8%), or housewives (6.5%). Most of the participants in the current study were nonsmokers (84.4%).

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of the participants (N=308)

Sociodemographic Data		n	%
Gender	Male	92	29.9%
	Female	216	70.1%
Age	19-29	100	32.5%
	30-39	76	24.7%
	40-49	84	27.3%
	50-59	48	15.6%
Marital status	Single	108	35.1%
	Married	200	64.9%
Education	Elementary education	28	9.1%
	Secondary education	16	5.2%
	Diploma	36	11.7%
	Bachelor's degree	168	54.5%
	Postgraduate education	60	19.5%
Occupation	Working	188	61.0%
	Not working	24	7.8%
	Student	76	24.7%

	Housewife	20	6.5%
Smoking	Yes	48	15.6%
	No	260	84.4%

Table 2 represents the medical history of the participants and reveals that more than 36.4% of the participants reported that they suffer from obesity, followed by 11.7% who have diabetes mellitus (DM) and 11.7% who

have hypertension (HTN). Additionally, only 23.4% of the participants reported that they had no previous medical history of any chronic diseases.

Table 2: Patients' medical histories and current illnesses

Patients Medical History	Yes		No	
	n	%	n	%
Neurologic disease	12	3.9%	296	96.1%
Immunological diseases	24	7.8%	284	92.2%
Osteoarthritis	24	7.8%	284	92.2%
COPD	4	1.3%	304	98.7%
DM	36	11.7%	272	88.3%
HTN	36	11.7%	272	88.3%
Coronary heart disease	12	3.9%	296	96.1%
Obesity	112	36.4%	196	63.6%
Osteoporosis	12	3.9%	296	96.1%
Psychiatric disease	8	2.6%	300	97.4%
Thyroid disorders	8	2.6%	300	97.4%
Others	28	9.1%	280	90.9%
No diseases	72	23.4%	236	76.6%

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Table 3 shows that the mean weight of the participants was 77.88 kg with a minimum of 40 kg and a maximum of 140 kg; also, the mean height of the participants was

163.36 cm with a minimum height of 120 cm and a maximum of 199 cm. Thus, the mean BMI of the participants was about 29 kg/m², which falls into the overweight category.

Table 3: Biometric measures of the participants (N=308)

Biometrics	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Weight Kg	40.0	140.0	77.883	21.0926
High cm	120.0	199.0	163.364	12.3678
BMI	16.65	45.20	29.0103	6.20725

We categorized the BMI of the participants into four groups: underweight (< 18.5 kg/m²), normal weight (18.5–24.9 kg/m²), overweight (25–29.9 kg/m²), and obese (≥ 30 kg/m²). (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2022). **Figure 1** below reflects that slightly more than two-fifths of the study sample were obese (41.9%) whereas about one-third of them were overweight (31.5%).

Figure 1: Participants' BMI categories

Table 4 represents the weight stigma scale for the participants using 12 statements measured on a scale ranging from strongly agree (1) to strongly disagree (5). However, the higher the score on the scale, the lower the participant's self-perceived weight stigma.

The findings revealed that the highest mean score was for statement number 12 (*Others are ashamed to be around me because of my weight*), meaning that most of the participants disagreed with this

statement, whereas the lowest mean score was for statement number 2 (*I caused my weight problems*), reflecting the highest agreement among the participants on this statement in the scale. Generally, the mean of the weight stigma scale was 3.4 ± 0.67 reflecting that about 60% disagreed with the statements of the scale versus 40% who agreed and had weight stigma (the lower the scale mean score, the greater the perceived weight stigma of the participants).

Table 4: Weight-Stigma Scale WSSQ

Weight-Stigma Scale	Strongly Agree		Agree		Neutral		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Mean	SD
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
1.I'll always go back to being overweight.	40	13.0%	108	35.1%	60	19.5%	72	23.4%	28	9.1%	2.81	1.20
2.I caused my weight problems.	36	11.7%	156	50.6%	48	15.6%	40	13.0%	28	9.1%	2.57	1.13
3.I feel guilty because of my weight problems.	60	19.5%	112	36.4%	44	14.3%	44	14.3%	48	15.6%	2.70	1.35
4.I became overweight because I am a weak person.	12	3.9%	56	18.2%	52	16.9%	100	32.5%	88	28.6%	3.64	1.19
5.I would never have any problems with weight if I was stronger.	44	14.3%	132	42.9%	56	18.2%	44	14.3%	32	10.4%	2.64	1.20
6.I don't have enough self-control to	44	14.3%	120	39.0%	60	19.5%	48	15.6%	36	11.7%	2.71	1.23

maintain a healthy weight.												
7.I feel insecure about others' opinions of me.	20	6.5%	68	22.1%	60	19.5%	100	32.5%	60	19.5%	3.36	1.21
8.People discriminate against me because I've had weight problems.	0	0.0%	24	7.8%	20	6.5%	136	44.2%	128	41.6%	4.19	0.87
9.It's difficult for people who haven't had weight problems to relate to me.	12	3.9%	8	2.6%	20	6.5%	136	44.2%	132	42.9%	4.19	0.96
10.Others will think I lack self-control because of my weight problems.	0	0.0%	40	13.0%	68	22.1%	84	27.3%	116	37.7%	3.90	1.05
11.People think that I am to blame for my weight problems.	0	0.0%	40	13.0%	68	22.1%	84	27.3%	116	37.7%	3.90	1.05
12.Others are ashamed to be around me because of my weight.	4	1.3%	16	5.2%	28	9.1%	112	36.4%	148	48.1%	4.25	0.92
Mean Weight-Stigma Scale	272	7%	880	24%	584	16%	1000	27%	960	26%	3.40	0.67

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Table 5 reflects the self-esteem scale of the participants using ten statements measured on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Five statements on the scale were positively stated (statement numbers 1, 3, 4, 7, and 10), and the other five statements were negatively stated. Thus, the scoring system of the negative statements was reverted to be in the same direction of the positive ones (1 strongly agree, 5 strongly disagree). The higher the score on the scale, the greater the participant's self-esteem.

The highest mean score of the scale was for statement number 6 (*I certainly feel useless at times*) meaning that most of the participants disagreed with this statement, whereas the lowest mean score of the scale was for statement number 8 (*I wish I could have more respect for myself*) reflecting the highest agreement of the participants on this statement (both statements' scores were reverted to become positive).

Overall, the mean score of the self-esteem scale was acceptable at 3.84 ± 0.6 reflecting a moderate to a high level of self-esteem among the participants (71%).

Table 5: Self-Esteem scale of the participants (RSE)

Self-Esteem scale	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	SD
	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%		
1. On the whole, I am satisfied with myself.	8	2.6%	56	18.2%	44	14.3%	140	45.5%	60	19.5%	3.61	1.07
2. At times I think I am no good at all.	12	3.9%	56	18.2%	56	18.2%	112	36.4%	72	23.4%	3.57	1.15

3. I feel that I have a number of good qualities.	4	1.3%	8	2.6%	16	5.2%	140	45.5%	140	45.5%	4.31	0.80
4. I am able to do things as well as most other people.	16	5.2%	8	2.6%	52	16.9%	132	42.9%	100	32.5%	3.95	1.03
5. I feel I do not have much to be proud of.	12	3.9%	12	3.9%	52	16.9%	108	35.1%	124	40.3%	4.04	1.04
6. I certainly feel useless at times.	0	0.0%	4	1.3%	36	11.7%	92	29.9%	176	57.1%	4.43	0.75
7. I feel that I'm a person of worth, at least on an equal plane with others.	36	11.7%	24	7.8%	56	18.2%	132	42.9%	60	19.5%	3.51	1.23
8. I wish I could have more respect for myself.	36	11.7%	112	36.4%	72	23.4%	36	11.7%	52	16.9%	2.86	1.27
9. All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am a failure.	4	1.3%	32	10.4%	32	10.4%	112	36.4%	128	41.6%	4.06	1.03
10. I take a positive attitude toward myself.	0	0.0%	24	7.8%	48	15.6%	136	44.2%	100	32.5%	4.01	0.89
Mean Self-Esteem scale	128	4%	336	11%	464	15%	1140	37%	1012	33%	3.84	0.60

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The higher the means self-esteem scale, the greater the self-esteem level of the participant, whereas the higher the mean weight stigma scale, the less the weight stigma feeling of the participant. **Table 6** shows a significant negative correlation between the BMI of the participants and their mean weight stigma scale and mean self-esteem scale, meaning that a higher BMI was

associated with more weight stigma and less self-esteem for the participants ($p < 0.01$).

Moreover, the results showed a positive significant correlation between the mean self-esteem scale and the mean weight stigma scale of the participants, reflecting that higher self-esteem feeling of the participants was positively associated with lower weight stigma feeling among them ($p < 0.01$).

Table 6: Correlation between the mean WSSQ, mean RSE scale, and BMI

Correlations			BMI	Mean weight stigma scale	Mean self-esteem scale
Spearman's rho	BMI	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.495**	-.428**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
		n	308	308	308
	Mean weight stigma scale	Correlation Coefficient	-.495**	1.000	.570**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
		n	308	308	308
	Mean self-esteem scale	Correlation Coefficient	-.428**	.570**	1.000

		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
		n	308	308	308

**** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

The linear regression equation in **Table 7** revealed that the mean weight stigma scale was a significant independent predictor of the mean self-esteem scale of the participants ($p < 0.01$).

Table 7: Linear regression equation for the WSSQ and the RSE scale mean scores

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.833	.201		4.144	.000
1 Mean self-esteem scale	.671	.052	.595	12.956	.000**

a. *Dependent variable: mean WSSQ*
**** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

The multiple regression equation in **Table 8** revealed that the gender of the participants, their age, and their smoking status were significant negative independent predictors of the weight stigma mean scale.

Older participants, those who smoke, and all female participants scored significantly lower on the mean weight stigma scale, meaning that they had significantly higher weight stigma feeling compared to younger participants, those who do not smoke, and all male participants in the current study.

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Table 8: Multiple regression of the WSSQ Scale with the sociodemographic variables

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.054	0.348		11.648	0.000
Gender	-0.333	0.094	-0.234	-3.556	.000**
Age	-0.118	0.047	-0.194	-2.481	.014*
1 Marital status	-0.112	0.127	-0.082	-0.877	0.381
Education	-0.069	0.038	-0.119	-1.825	0.069
Occupation	0.054	0.034	0.123	1.597	0.111
Smoking	-0.266	0.108	-0.148	-2.458	.015*

a. *Dependent variable: mean WSSQ*
**** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**
*** Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

Table 9 represents the multiple regression of the mean self-esteem scale and reflects that marital status was the only

significant negative independent predictor of the participants' mean self-esteem scale.

To illustrate, married participants had significantly lower mean self-esteem scores, indicating that they had generally lower self-

esteem feelings compared to single participants.

Table 9: Multiple regression of the RSE Scale with the sociodemographic variables

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. error	Beta		
(Constant)	4.604	0.325		14.145	0
Gender	0.08	0.088	0.062	0.917	0.36
Age	0.001	0.044	0.002	0.02	0.984
1 Marital status	-0.376	0.119	-0.305	-3.156	.002**
Education	-0.005	0.035	-0.01	-0.147	0.883
Occupation	-0.024	0.032	-0.059	-0.744	0.458
Smoking	-0.09	0.101	-0.056	-0.889	0.375

a. Dependent variable: Mean RSE Scale
 ** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

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Table 10 shows the correlation between participants' chronic medical diseases and the BMIs of the participants.

Higher BMIs of the participants were significantly correlated with osteoarthritis, DM, HTN, obesity, and osteoporosis.

Table 10: The correlation between the participants' BMI and their chronic illnesses

Correlations		BMI	
Spearman's rho	Smoking	Correlation coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.002 .978
	Neurologic disease	Correlation coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.057 .316
	Immunological diseases	Correlation coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	-.080 .164
	Osteoarthritis	Correlation coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.117* .041
	COPD	Correlation coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.036 .528
	DM	Correlation coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.172** .002
	HTN	Correlation coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.172** .002
	Coronary heart disease	Correlation coefficient	.066

	Obesity	Sig. (2-tailed)	.245
		Correlation coefficient	.522**
	Osteoporosis	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
		Correlation coefficient	.160**
	Psychiatric disease	Sig. (2-tailed)	.005
		Correlation coefficient	.004
Thyroid disorders	Sig. (2-tailed)	.949	
	Correlation coefficient	.042	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.460

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Discussion

The results of our current study demonstrate that most of the study sample was female and married, about one-third were aged 19–29 years, and slightly more than half held a bachelor’s degree. Most of the study sample worked and did not smoke. Regarding chronic illness, slightly more than one-third of the study population reported that they have obesity, and one-tenth of them have DM and HTN; also, the higher BMIs of the participants was significantly correlated with having osteoarthritis, DM, HTN, obesity, and osteoporosis. In interpretation, obesity is considered a risk factor for many chronic noncommunicable diseases. This result was accepted by Kinlen and his colleagues in their study on complications of obesity. They reported that obesity is a severe health issue that can lead to serious side effects like DM, HTN, and cardiovascular disease. It has a strong link to cancer, stroke, asthma, and decreased fertility (Kinlen et al., 2018). Moreover, prior research found a positive correlation between perceived weight discrimination and physiological dysregulation, as measured by cardiovascular, inflammatory, lipid, and metabolic dysregulation (Daly et al., 2019); and a negative correlation between stigma and excess weight and allostatic load (measured using 7 systems: sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous system, hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis,

cardiovascular functioning, general and specific immune function, and lipid metabolism;(Jackson & Steptoe, 2017).

Our research revealed that the mean WSSQ was 3.4 ± 0.67 , reflecting around 60% of the participants who disagreed with the scale statements versus 40% who agreed and had significant weight stigma (the lower the WSSQ mean score, the greater the weight stigma of the participants). The percentage of those having weight stigma is quite close to the results of a previous nationwide cross-sectional study conducted in Saudi Arabia and showed that the prevalence of weight stigma in Saudi Arabia is relatively high at 46.4% (Althumiri, Basyouni, AlMousa, et al., 2021). Similarly, in a three-sample study conducted in the United States (Puhl et al., 2018), researchers reported that at least 44% of adults across the samples exceeded the mean level of weight-based internalization.

The findings of our current study indicate that the mean score of the self-esteem scale was acceptable, reflecting a moderate to high level of self-esteem among the participants. Also, there was a significant negative correlation between the BMI of the participants and both the mean weight stigma scale and mean self-esteem scale, meaning that higher BMIs of the participants were associated with higher weight stigma and lower self-esteem. Additionally, the results showed a positive significant correlation between the mean self-esteem scale and the

mean weight stigma scale of the participants, reflecting that higher self-esteem feelings of the participants were positively associated with lower weight stigma. This result coincided with a Polish study that revealed that excess BMI typically co-occurred with experiences of weight-related stigma. However, compared with those who had an above average BMI, a substantially higher percentage of respondents reported having been stigmatized because of their weight (Jach & Krystoń, 2021). Likewise, in adults, associations between weight stigma, BMI, and difficulties decreasing weight were discovered by Papadopoulos and Brennan (2015).

Our findings revealed that the mean WSSQ was a significant independent predictor of the participants' mean RSE scale, which indicates weight stigma's psychological impact on self-esteem. This result was supported by many previous studies showing that anxiety, despair, low self-esteem, substance abuse, binge eating disorders, bulimia nervosa, and anorexia nervosa have all been linked to weight stigma (Papadopoulos & Brennan, 2015; Puhl & Suh, 2015a, 2015b). Similarly, lower self-esteem and higher body dissatisfaction were reported by those who experienced weight stigma, as reported by Vartanian and Novak (2011).

In the same context, and independent of BMI, research has shown that those who experience weight-related discrimination are more likely to engage in behaviors that contribute to the development of obesity, such as disordered eating (Ashmore et al., 2008), increased calories intake (Major et al., 2014; Schvey et al., 2011), and avoidance of physical activity (Vartanian & Novak, 2011). They were also more likely to gain weight over time (Jackson et al., 2014).

Those who suffered weight stigmatization reported lower self-esteem and higher body dissatisfaction (Vartanian & Novak, 2011). Additionally, longitudinal data from the Midlife in the United States study (MIDUS) revealed that weight discrimination makes obesity's negative effects on self-reported functional mobility worse. This may be because weight discrimination damages

self-perception as a capable, fully functional individual (Schafer & Ferraro, 2011).

In our current study, older participants, those who smoke, and all female participants scored significantly lower on the mean weight stigma scale, meaning that they had significantly higher weight stigma feelings, and that female gender, older age, and smoking were considered risk factors for more intense feelings of weight stigma. People who feel weight stigmatized may feel psychological stress and may engage in undisciplined behavior. Older people may have less physical mobility and be less active which may result in weight gain and feelings of weight stigma. Also, married participants had significantly lower means self-esteem scores compared to single participants which may be related to the feeling of low self-esteem associated with the perceived body image disturbance and the partner's dissatisfaction with the participant's changes in body weight.

The results of our current study echo those of Runfola et al. (2013), who found that women may feel less gratified by their bodies because they are expected to conform to the ideal physical appearance more than males, which could result in a higher incidence of psychological consequences like sadness and low self-esteem. In the same context, a meta-analysis study indicated that people with class I obesity (BMI = 30–34.99 kg/m²) and people with class II obesity (BMI ≥ 35 kg/m²) reported a prevalence of perceived weight discrimination of 19.2% and 41.8% respectively, with women reporting a higher prevalence of perceived weight discrimination (Spahlholz et al., 2016). Similarly, another former study uncovered evidence that weight discrimination may be associated with lower levels of regular physical exercise and higher levels of sedentary behavior (Jackson & Steptoe, 2017). Moreover, the feelings of weight stigma take individuals away from healthy self-care behaviors (Pearl et al., 2015).

Conclusion

We concluded that more than one-third of the reporting participants suffered from obesity, followed by people who have DM and HTN. Slightly more than two-fifths of

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the study sample were obese while about one-third were overweight.

More than half of the participants disagreed with the statements on the weight stigma scale, and the means score of the self-esteem scale reflected a moderate to a high level of self-esteem among the participants (71%). Moreover, the study revealed a significant negative correlation between the BMIs of the participants and both their mean weight stigma scale and mean self-esteem scale, meaning that higher BMIs among the participants were associated with feelings of higher weight stigma and lower self-esteem.

The mean weight stigma scale was a significant independent predictor of the mean self-esteem scale of the participants. Also, the positive significant correlation between the mean self-esteem scale and the mean weight stigma scale of the participants reflected the association of higher feeling of self-esteem with lower weight stigma among participants.

Furthermore, older participants, those who smoke, and all female participants scored significantly lower on the mean weight stigma scale, meaning that they had significantly higher weight stigma feeling in our current study. Additionally, married participants had lower self-esteem feeling compared to single participants. Finally, our findings also showed a correlation between the patients' chronic medical diseases and the BMIs of the participants. Higher participant BMIs were significantly correlated with osteoarthritis, DM, HTN, obesity, and osteoporosis.

Recommendations

It is important to conduct more research to investigate the overweight population and weight stigma phenomena by taking a larger sample size and including different communities compared with those in our present study.

A psychoeducational program is one of the key interventions to increase public awareness about weight management and weight stigma in communities. Such a program will improve coping abilities with physical and psychological negative consequences associated with obesity and instill the importance of following a healthy lifestyle.

Moreover, it can be helpful to focus the mass media's attention on the importance of maintaining normal body weight and the dangers of being overweight and developing many chronic diseases like DM, HTN, osteoarthritis, osteoporosis, and many others. Additionally, educational programs about maintaining normal body weight should be initiated for adolescents still in school as well as adults and elderly people.

Study limitations: The use of cross-sectional research design is one of the greatest limitations of the current study design. Also, randomization is very important to reach better findings' generalizability.

Abbreviations: (BMI) Body Mass Index, (DM) Diabetes Mellitus, (RSE) Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, (WSSQ) Weight Self-Stigma Questionnaire, (MIDUS) Midlife in the United States.

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